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Deliverable D3.7

D-NA2.3c Summary Report on Trans-national Access Calls

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	7
1. Introduction	8
1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document	8
1.2 Structure of the Document	8
2. Lab Access Calls Timeline	9
3. Lab Access Dissemination Material and Channels	10
3.1 Project Website	10
3.2 Flyer.....	11
3.3 Newsletter	11
3.4 Social Networks.....	12
3.5 Presentation Slides	13
4. Consortium’s Dissemination of Lab Access Calls	14
5. Outcomes of Lab Access Calls Dissemination.....	16
6. Conclusions	17
References	18
Appendix A: Project Website.....	19
Appendix B: Example of a Lab Access Page	20
Appendix C: Project Flyer.....	21
Appendix D: Latest Project Newsletter	22
Appendix E: Lab Access Slide.....	23

List of Figures

Figure 1: Pageviews of the Trans-national Access (TA) subpage.	10
Figure 2: Example of exposure on X (Twitter) during the last 11 months.	12
Figure 3: Example of the call announcement on LinkedIn.	13
Figure 4: ERIGrid 2.0 followers by organisation type.	17

List of Tables

Table 1: Overview of the consortium's dissemination efforts.	14
Table 2: Outcomes of promotion through channels.	16

List of Abbreviations

DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
MTR	Mid-Term Review
NA	Networking Activities
PoC	Person of Contact
RI	Research Infrastructure
RTD	Research and Technology Development
TA	Trans-national Access
USP	User Selection Panel
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

In this document, the efforts of the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium for the dissemination of the Trans-national Access programme in the time frame from 1 May 2023 to 30 September 2024 are reported, as well as the results of these efforts for TA Calls 9-13.

The documentation for Trans-national Access dissemination includes specific details about the materials and channels used, along with examples of activities carried out. The channels used for disseminating information about the Trans-national Access programme include the project website, various social media platforms, the project newsletter, presentation slides and others.

In addition to the dissemination activities undertaken in WP3-NA2 led by DERlab as Work Package Leader, the report contains a brief overview of the activities of other partners for the dissemination of ERIGrid 2.0's Trans-national Access programme.

Lastly, the report provides details on the number of Trans-national Access proposals received for each call and the success rate of each dissemination channel. Based on this information, the report draws conclusions about the effectiveness of each channel. Finally, the report concludes by discussing the lessons learnt from the project and the measures that will be taken to promote the Trans-national Access program going forward, taking into account the project's progress to date and the established goals.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document is the third and final summary report on TA dissemination activities of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. It presents a summary of the efforts for the promotion of TA opportunities undertaken by DERlab as Work Package Leader (WPL) of Work Package (WP) 3 – Networking Activities (NA) 2 as well as the rest of the consortium members. This deliverable also presents the marketing materials that have been developed and the channels that have been used to ensure the effective promotion of this activity.

Within its TAs, ERIGrid 2.0 offers external users free access to the Research Infrastructures (RIs) of the consortium partners, including funding for travel expenses, accommodation, subsistence costs, as well as scientific and dissemination support. This offer is primarily intended to benefit individuals and organisations in the research, academic, and industrial sectors focused on power system testing, smart grids, and energy systems. Through this activity, research projects in compliance with European Research and Technology Developments (RTDs) priorities and with the prospect of social impact and impact on European Union (EU) industry are supported. The TA programme aims to support new smart energy solutions and the development of an integrated European RI (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019).

As a set of channels and a significant following on each of them have been achieved in the predecessor project ERIGrid, ERIGrid 2.0 decided to continue using these accounts in the new project after necessary adjustment and re-branding. This enabled the consortium to ensure the transfer of best practices between the projects, maintaining momentum and effectively reaching the target audience. Moreover, to use a more comprehensive vocabulary towards the project-external persons, it was decided within the consortium to use the term “Lab Access” (similar to “TA”) for public promotion outside the project.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The structure of the document is organised as follows: Section 2 introduces the timeline for the TA calls. Section 3 presents materials and channels established for the promotion and how they have been used. Section 4 provides an overview of activities performed by consortium members. Section 5 presents the outcomes of the activities. The report is concluded in Section 6. Finally, images of the developed and used dissemination and marketing material are provided in Appendix A, Appendix B, Appendix C, Appendix D and Appendix E.

2 Lab Access Calls Timeline

The ERIGrid 2.0 TA programme is organised into three-month time windows, during which external users can submit their lab access applications. The calls are launched every four months, with one calendar month reserved between the closing date of the previous call and the opening date of the next call.

The current report covers the time frame of the following TA calls and therefore presents the promotion efforts made during and between these:

- Call 9: 1 June 2023 – 31 August 2023
- Call 10: 1 October 2023 – 31 December 2023
- Call 11: 10 January 2024 – 31 March 2024
- Call 12: 1 April 2024 – 30 June 2024
- Call 13: 1 July 2024 – 30 September 2024

Note that, due to the extension of the ERIGrid 2.0 project, three extra calls (11, 12 and 13) were added with respect to the initial planning.

3 Lab Access Dissemination Material and Channels

This section is about the materials and channels that ERIGrid 2.0 is using as promotional tools for the TA opportunities: the project website, the project flyer, the newsletter, the promotion on social networks, as well as the general presentation slides.

3.1 Project Website

The primary source of public information about ERIGrid 2.0, including its activities and results, can be found on the project website¹. The website gives significant coverage of the TA programme, with a dedicated page created specifically to provide comprehensive and easy-accessible information about it. The consortium has taken great care to offer as much assistance as possible to individuals interested in applying (see Appendix A). The dedicated lab access subpage² provides important information for potential applicants, including valuable details that can help guide them through the application process:

- Overview of the TA, its intended audience, and what kind of assistance is provided by the programme,
- Timeline of the prior and future TA calls,
- A comprehensive overview of the available facilities, with the ability to filter them by specific categories: “Transient Power System Dynamics and Control Validation” or “Smart Energy Systems Integration and Validation”,
- Detailed, step-by-step guidelines for potential users on how to submit their applications
- Criteria for selection,
- Associated documents or required templates: lab access guide, proposal template, link to the proposal submission platform, contract model, test canvas template, and report template, and
- FAQ section, consistently updated based on regular communication with applicants.

The TA subpage gathered over 200 views every month for the past year. The highest page views in 2024 were in the month of January, collecting more than 500 views, as outlined in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Pageviews of the TA subpage.

Each facility listed in the overview on this page is connected to a separate page containing detailed information about the RI offered at the respective facility, services provided, lab access

¹<https://erigrd2.eu>

²<https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access>

conditions and additional pertinent information, including videos and pictures. Additionally, each lab page includes a contact form that allows prospective applicants to pose any questions they might have. The submitted forms are automatically sent to the Person of Contact (PoC) of the corresponding labs. An example of a lab page is given in Appendix B.

Additionally, relevant for the TA and cross-linked from the TA subpage are the following two subpages:

- “*User Projects*³” presenting the list of implemented TA user projects, and
- “*Selection Panel*⁴” providing the list of the User Selection Panel (USP) members in order to ensure transparency and allow applicants to identify any potential conflicts of interest in their submissions.

As the number of user projects grew, the consortium prepared a dedicated subpage entitled “*Success Stories*⁵” to showcase successful examples of TA user research. This measure will contribute to the dissemination of the results as set out in the Grant Agreement (GA) (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019) and to attract even more potential TA users.

3.2 Flyer

The project flyer (see Appendix C) includes information about the TA program. This was implemented to ensure that the program receives adequate attention and promotion alongside other project elements. The flyer offers key information on the TA program, such as general details, the application timeline, and references to additional information. It has been created for distribution and sharing at a variety of events, including conferences, trade fairs, meetings, and networking opportunities.

3.3 Newsletter

At the beginning of the project, a newsletter template was developed to ensure consistency. This newsletter features the latest updates and opportunities, including information about the TA program and other related details, and is regularly distributed to over 650 subscribers. From May 2023 up to the date of writing this document, five newsletters⁶ have been released, out of which all five advertised TA and corresponding calls. The average open rate across the newsletters varies between approximately 30% and 40%, which is considered a good rate for newsletters. An example of the latest newsletter, which was sent out in September 2024, shows the promotion of the TA Call 13 in Appendix D. An important collaboration in promoting the TA and corresponding calls has been the promotion offered by the European Universities Association. From November 2023, throughout this collaboration both TA calls and other ERIGrid 2.0 activities have been promoted through their website by featuring ERIGrid 2.0 in articles and in their newsletter.

³<https://erigrd2.eu/user-projects>

⁴<https://erigrd2.eu/selection-panel>

⁵<https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access/success-stories/>

⁶<https://erigrd2.eu/resources#newsletters>

3.4 Social Networks

ERIGrid 2.0 uses social networks *LinkedIn*⁷ and *X (Twitter)*⁸ for general project promotion and TA dissemination.

At the time of writing, ERIGrid 2.0 has over 2,250 followers on LinkedIn and almost 550 followers on X (Twitter). An exemplification of TA updates on X (Twitter) and the reached engagement is presented in Figure 2. Moreover, all past calls were advertised (see Figure 3) extensively, including:

- Pinning the new call announcement on top of the LinkedIn or X (Twitter) page so anyone who visited the social media and was interested to apply, saw the new call first thing, and
- Regular updates highlighting the RI of each facility.

Figure 2: Example of exposure on X (Twitter) during the last 11 months.

⁷<https://www.linkedin.com/company/erigrd-project>

⁸<https://twitter.com/ERIGrid>

The ERIGrid 2.0 Project
 2,261 followers
 3mo · 🌐

🚨 **This will be the last submission possibility in ERIGrid 2.0 !**
 A new Lab Access Call is now open! The 13th call will be open until the end of September 2024.

All interested engineers involved in the domains of power system testing, smart grids and energy systems are invited to receive free funding to access the best laboratories of Europe and perform their own experimental research.

🔗 Make sure you visit the ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access page for detailed information on the application process: <https://lnkd.in/evBCF9s>

Apply now!

#ERIGrid #labaccess #applynow

The graphic is a green rectangular poster with the text 'NEW CALL' at the top and bottom in large, white, serif font. In the center, there is a white box containing the ERIGrid 2.0 logo (with the tagline 'Connecting European Smart Grid Infrastructures') and the following text: 'Last submission possibility in ERIGrid 2.0!', 'The 13th Lab Access Call is open now until September 30th 2024.', and 'Apply now!' in red.

You and 34 others · 7 reposts

Figure 3: Example of the call announcement on LinkedIn.

3.5 Presentation Slides

The project consortium created a project presentation to share information at pertinent events and conferences. One slide in the presentation is specifically devoted to highlighting the TA programme. This slide includes a map displaying the available facilities, their logos, and a reference for obtaining more information. By including the TA program into the presentation, the project gains a wider exposure as project partners participate in various events where the ERIGrid 2.0 target audience is present.

4 Consortium's Dissemination of Lab Access Calls

Table 1 provides an overview of the dissemination efforts undertaken by the consortium.

Table 1: Overview of the consortium's dissemination efforts.

Partner	Type of Activity	Event, Platform, Channel	Location, Time	Type, Size of Audience
DERlab	Updates and posts	Social Media (LinkedIn), Website	Regular and ongoing	Research, academia, industry; ca. 1,200 followers
DERlab	Email promotion	Email	During TA calls	Research; ca. 200 newsletter subscribers; broad international networks (ISGAN Annex 5 SIRFN, ETIP SNET, EERA JP Smart Grids, BRIDGE)
OFFIS	Updates and posts	Social Media (LinkedIn)	During TA Calls, after TA completion at the SESA laboratory	Research institutes, universities, companies, ca. 5,000 followers
CRES	Updates and posts	Organisation's website	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, companies
CRES	Email promotion	Email	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, companies, including the consortium of GIFT (H2020)
CRES	Promotion	Presentation	During bilateral meetings	Industry, SMEs
JRC	Email promotion	Email	Regular and ongoing	European research institutions and private companies operating in the energy sector
VTT	Updates and posts	Social Media (LinkedIn), Organisation's website	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, companies
VTT	Email promotion	Email	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, companies
VTT	Workshops, Tutorials, Webinars, Fairs	Presentation	EES-UETP Workshop on Advanced Laboratory System Testing Methods for Modern Power Systems 2023	Research institutes, universities, companies
AIT	Updates and posts	Social Media (LinkedIn), Organisation's website, AIT Social Media Channel	During TA calls, posts during lab access	Research institutes, universities, personal contacts, companies
AIT	Email promotion	Email	Regular and ongoing, especially directed to former users and their institutions	Research institutes, universities, companies, personal contacts

Partner	Type of Activity	Event, Platform, Channel	Location, Time	Type, Size of Audience
AIT	Conferences, Workshops, Tutorials, Webinars, Fairs	Presentation	PVSEC-34, EEE-AM 2023, DERlab GA, DigiSect 2023, CIRED 2023 and 2024 and AIT WS, OSMSES 2024, RI Automation Workshop 2024, etc.	Research institutes, universities, companies
ICCS	Email promotion	Email	Regular and ongoing	Research institutes, universities, companies, personal contacts
ICCS	Updates and posts	Social Media (LinkedIn)	During TA calls, posts after TA completion	Research institutes, universities, personal contacts, companies
ICCS	Seminars, Panel Sessions, Tutorials	Presentation	DERlab GA, ERIGrid 2.0 Summer School, OSMSES 2024	Research institutes, universities, companies
TECNALIA	Promotion	Presentation	During multiple visits to TECNALIA's facilities	Research institutes, universities, industrial companies
TECNALIA	TA Programme explanation	Phone and Email	Direct interactions with partners and customers	Research institutes, universities, industrial companies
RSE	Updates and posts	Social Media Channels, LinkedIn	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, personal contacts, companies
RSE	Email promotion	Email	Regular and ongoing	Research institutes, universities, companies, personal contacts
OCT	Updates and posts	Social Media Channels (LinkedIn, Twitter)	Regular and ongoing	Research institutes, universities, personal contacts, companies
UCY-FOSS	Updates and posts	Social Media Channels, LinkedIn	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, personal contacts, companies
UCY-FOSS	Email promotion	Email	Regular and ongoing	Research institutes, universities, companies, personal contacts
SINTEF	Email promotion	Email	During TA calls	Research institutes, universities, companies, personal contacts
SINTEF	Updates and posts	Social media (WhatsApp)	During TA calls	Regular message with link to TA access to researchers groups
SINTEF	Updates and posts	Webinars, meetings	Regular and ongoing	Research institutes, universities, companies

5 Outcomes of Lab Access Calls Dissemination

In the five TA calls reported in this document, the consortium received 44 proposals. Based on preliminary estimations, that number amounts to approximately 316 access days (19.1% of the objective in the Description of Action (DoA)) for Calls 9-12 (Call 13 is not yet evaluated). Having completed 12 calls and with Call 13 in evaluation at the time of writing, the consortium does not foresee additional calls. Assuming that the consortium maintains the rate of received TA proposals, the target of access days can be achieved.

The DoA set out the goal of at least 25% of the executed user projects must involve industry participation. The progress estimation upon completion of Call 12 lies at approximately 18%.

For effective dissemination of TA calls, it has been important for the consortium to know which of the promotion channels used results in the most results in terms of the number of proposals submitted in each call. For that purpose, questions about how the applicants had learnt about the TA was included in the TA application procedure. The responses collected are summarised in Table 2, which presents the results of dissemination through specific channels. Applicants frequently indicate multiple sources of their initial knowledge of ERIGrid 2.0, therefore, the number of proposals for all sources indicated for a specific call may collectively exceed the number of actual proposals received in the call.

Table 2: Outcomes of promotion through channels.

	Call 9 5 proposals	Call 10 16 proposals	Call 11 6 proposals	Call 12 5 proposals	Call 13 12 proposals
Personal recommendation by project partner	2	3	4	-	3
Previous connection with ERIGrid	-	2	1	1	3
Website	1	2	1	1	-
Social media	1	3	-	1	1
Involved in ERIGrid 2.0	-	2	-	1	1
Project partner email promotion	1	1	-	1	4
Event	-	3	-	-	-
PowerGlobe Forum	-	-	-	-	-
Newsletter	-	-	-	-	-

As seen from the collected answers, the highest number of proposals, collectively for Calls 9 to 13, as well as for each call, came as a result of individual promotion directed to personal contacts. The second most efficient way to receive proposals is through a previous connection and past knowledge of the predecessor project ERIGrid. The following most effective channels are involvement within ERIGrid 2.0 and through events and conferences as well as social media (LinkedIn).

6 Conclusions

It can be concluded from the outcomes of the TA calls that the most successful means of obtaining proposals was through individual partners' promotion and personal recommendations to potential applicants. Therefore, the consortium put more focus on this channel, although other dissemination channels supported it to gain more visibility. As more ERIGrid 2.0 events were organised later on in the project, there were be more opportunities for the partners for such networking activities.

Furthermore, according to the recommendations resulting from the Mid-Term Review (MTR) of the ERIGrid 2.0 project (i.e., on 02/02/2022), more focus was put on the general dissemination of the work and the promotion of the access to the lab facilities, beyond the project partners and their direct research communities. Thanks to social media analytics (particularly LinkedIn), it can be seen that the largest part of ERIGrid 2.0's audience came from the engineering sector, followed directly by research and education (see Figure 4). As the project was already quite established within the research community, more effort was put into reaching a wider audience such as the general public or policymakers. This allowed the project to gain more visibility and awareness and thus increased the project's impact.

Figure 4: ERIGrid 2.0 followers by organisation type.

Another way to reach a wider audience was by offering engaging content. An example of a measure that has been put in place to address this is the creation of "Success Story" templates, to share, in an easy-to-read way, the positive research experiences and results enabled by the TA calls. These were shared and promoted through the project website, social media channels, newsletters and relevant events and conferences.

References

ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement. (2019). European Commission.

Appendix A: Project Website

GET FREE ACCESS TO LEADING SMART GRID AND ENERGY SYSTEMS LABS AND SERVICES

ERIGRID 2.0 invites all interested engineers involved in the domains of power system testing, smart grids and energy systems to receive free funding to access the best laboratories of Europe and perform their own experimental research. There are two kinds of lab access services available in ERIGRID 2.0:

FREE ACCESS TO 21 PHYSICAL LABS

Physical free access to our laboratories can be performed on-site at the location of the lab or remotely if the infrastructure allows. To get this access you need to apply as described below and to be selected by the independent User Selection Panel (USP).

If your application is successful, you will receive funding for your research stay at the location of the laboratory you selected, completely covering the following expenses:

- Travelling
- Accommodation
- All lab operation costs and physical lab access to ERIGRID 2.0 testing and simulation facilities
- Access to concentrated know-how and best practices in the field of smart grid and energy systems, such as power system components, characterisation and evaluation, smart grid ICT/automation, validation, co-simulation, real-time simulation and Power/Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL), and others.

IMPORTANT UPDATE JULY 2023: Lab access applications can only be considered from user groups coming from the European Union and/or Associated Countries! Further details are provided in the FAQ.

APPLY NOW UNTIL SEPTEMBER 30TH, 2024!

Please note that applications close automatically on the date of the deadline, and no late applications can be accepted.

The schedule of calls for lab access applications is as follows:

- 1st call: 1 October 2020 – 31 December 2020 (closed)
- 2nd call: 1 February 2021 – 30 April 2021 (closed)
- 3rd call: 1 June 2021 – 31 August 2021 (closed)
- 4th call: 1 October 2021 – 31 December 2021 (closed)
- 5th call: 1 February 2022 – 30 April 2022 (closed)
- 6th call: 1 June 2022 – 31 August 2022 (closed)
- 7th call: 1 October 2022 – 31 December 2022 (closed)
- 8th call: 1 February 2023 – 30 April 2023 (closed)
- 9th call: 1 June 2023 – 31 August 2023 (closed)
- 10th call: 1 October 2023 – 31 December 2023 (closed)
- 11th call: 10 January 2024 – 31 March 2024 (closed)
- 12th call: 1 April 2024 – 30 June 2024 (closed)
- 13th call: 1 July 2024 – 30 September 2024 - **test submission possibility in ERIGRID 2.0!**

[Subscribe to Newsletter](#)

To stay informed about the lab access programme and detailed descriptions of the facilities and services, bookmark this page or just subscribe to the **ERIGRID newsletter** to receive all the updates, directly in your inbox.

FREE ACCESS TO 10 VIRTUAL FACILITIES

The access to the virtual facilities requires no specific application and user proposals are not submitted to a selection process.

You can access and start using the free virtual services right away taking the following points into account:

- The provided virtual data, services and resources are openly and freely available under open access licenses through communication networks.
- Access to virtual services allows for a quick, easy and casual access to existing virtual resources by eliminating administrative obstacles.
- Users can try the provided virtual services without obligations.
- No individual support or supervision is offered to the users.

PHYSICAL LAB ACCESS APPLICATION PROCESS

Identify your experimental needs: empirical topic and testing/validation goals

Select potential labs (up to 3) which are suitable for your topic

Build up your team or decide to apply as an individual user

Write the proposal using this template

Your proposal will be evaluated by independent reviewers from this list – Please point out any names that may involve a conflict of interest in the proposal submission system

Register yourself in the proposal submission system and submit your proposal – list all user group members in the submission system (see list as in the proposal)

ERIGRID 2.0 partners offer a wide range of installations and competences to assist successful applicants with conducting experiments. Such a common framework of applied smart grid expertise will accelerate the development of an integrated pan-European research infrastructure.

Thomas Strasser (AIT)
Coordinator of ERIGRID 2.0

- Lab Access Guide
- Proposal Template
- Proposal Submission
- Contract Booklet
- Test Canvas Template
- Report Template

PHYSICAL LAB ACCESS SELECTION CRITERIA

Your proposal for physical lab access must meet the following criteria:

- Scientific and technical relevance, originality and innovation, methodology, robust and realistic test/evaluation approach
- Prospect of knowledge enhancement at the research infrastructures
- Completeness and organisation of the proposal, clear definition of the objectives and expected results, relevance of the proposed dissemination actions, justified amount of requested access
- Compliance with European RTD policies and priorities; prospect of social impact and impact on EU industry. New users, young researchers, female researchers are especially welcome.

IMPORTANT UPDATE JULY 2023: Lab access applications can only be considered from user groups coming from the European Union and/or Associated Countries! Further details are provided in the FAQ.

The evaluation will be performed by the User Selection Panel, an international independent group of experts with diverse profiles (academia, industry) covering the different domains of the smart energy systems (power systems, ICT, etc.). In parallel, a technical and economic feasibility check for the potential lab implementation will be done by the addressed ERIGRID 2.0 infrastructures.

CITING THE ERIGRID 2.0 VIRTUAL FACILITIES

If you use the ERIGRID 2.0 Virtual Facilities in your research reports, articles and conferences, we would appreciate that you acknowledge us, as follows:

"This research has been performed using the ERIGRID 2.0 Virtual Facilities and is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Grant Agreement No. 870420. The support of the European Research Infrastructure ERIGRID 2.0 and its partners is very much appreciated."

PHYSICAL LABS AND VIRTUAL SERVICES

Access to physical labs can be on-site or remote, depending on the conditions of specific laboratories. To know if remote access can be organised in your case, please contact the laboratory staff through corresponding subpages below.

ALL	ON-SITE AND REMOTE TRANSIENT POWER SYSTEM DYNAMICS AND CONTROL VALIDATION	ON-SITE AND REMOTE SMART ENERGY SYSTEMS INTEGRATION AND VALIDATION	VIRTUAL FACILITIES

Appendix B: Example of a Lab Access Page

SMART GRID COMMUNICATION LABORATORY (HEDNO)

The Smart Grid Communication Laboratory (SGC-Lab) constitutes a part of the Voice and Data Communication Section of the Information Technology & Telecommunications Department of HEDNO. It aims to develop and administer the communication network of HEDNO in the framework of smart grid communications.

More specifically, the laboratory's scope is the evaluation of communication technologies suitable for remote monitoring and remote control of the Greek distribution grid. Moreover, the SGC-Lab seeks to establish research and laboratory facilities to provide added value operational guidelines and information to production systems (Operational and Information Technology).

Location: HEDNO - Athens, Greece

www.deddie.gr

[+ DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE](#)

[+ SERVICES OFFERED](#)

[+ DESCRIPTION OF THE ORGANIZATION](#)

[+ LAB ACCESS CONDITIONS OFFERED BY HEDNO](#)

Appendix C: Project Flyer

FREE PHYSICAL AND VIRTUAL LAB ACCESS

The ERIGrid 2.0 project invites all interested engineers in the domains of power system testing, smart grids and smart energy to receive free funding to access the best laboratories and services of Europe for their own experimental research. Physical lab access can be organised either on-site or remotely. Furthermore, ERIGrid 2.0 provides virtual access to 8 facilities and services without applications required.

USERS WILL RECEIVE:

- on-site or remote access to 21 first-class laboratories or application-free virtual access to 8 services of ERIGrid partners
- in case of physical access: funding for their complete research stay at the location of the selected laboratory, including coverage of expenses for travelling, accommodation and lab operation costs
- access to concentrated know-how and best practices in the field of smart grids and energy systems components characterisation and evaluation, smart grid ICT / automation validation, co-simulation, real-time simulation and Power/Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL), and others
- opportunity to advance their own research and solutions
- working with the top smart grid and energy systems experts
- chance to impact EU industry
- promotion of their research through ERIGrid 2.0 channels

Find detailed descriptions of labs and services and all further details at erigrd2.eu/lab-access.

apply every 3 months for physical lab access

access virtual services anytime no application required

CONSORTIUM COORDINATED BY

CONNECTING EUROPEAN SMART GRID RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

FREE ACCESS TO EUROPE'S BEST SMART GRID AND ENERGY SYSTEMS LABS

@ERIGrid 2.0 Project

www.erigrd2.eu

Supported by the H2020 Programme under Contract No. 870620

Based on the results from the predecessor project ERIGrid-1, ERIGrid 2.0 will expand the research services and tools of research infrastructures for validating smart energy networks with the electric power grid as the main backbone.

ABOUT

- ERIGrid 2.0: European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition
- 20 partners from research, academia and industry
- 21 first-class European labs provided to external users for free access on-site or remotely
- 8 facilities and services provided to external users for virtual access
- 13 European countries represented in the consortium
- Duration: 1 April 2020 – 30 September 2024
- Budget: €10M funded by the European Commission

ERIGrid 2.0 – European RI for Smart Grids, Smart Energy Systems, and Renewables Research

SUSTAINABLE, LOW-CARBON ENERGY POLICY

- 2015 Paris Agreement
- EU "Clean Energy for All Europeans" package
- EU Vision 2050

EU Energy Transition Goal: Creation of a low-carbon, secure, reliable, resilient, accessible, cost-efficient, and market-based pan-European integrated energy system

Goals:

- support the research, technology development, and innovation of smart grid and smart energy systems approaches, concepts, and solutions in Europe taking a holistic and cyber-physical systems-based approach into account
- provide system-level support and education for industrial and academic researchers in power and energy systems research and technology development

Networking Objectives:

- knowledge-exchange with other European smart grid and smart energy systems RIs
- knowledge transfer between researchers, technicians, and RI managers
- Open Access (OA) provision of achievements and reinforced collaboration with industry and energy utilities
- education of power and energy system professionals
- international collaboration and harmonization

Appendix D: Latest Project Newsletter

Connecting European Smart Grid Infrastructures

European Research Infrastructure Supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll out - Second Edition

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In this issue:

- [Last Lab Access Call Open Until 30th of September 2024](#)
- [Register Now for the RI Automation Workshop in Denmark!](#)
- [ERIGrid 2.0's Successful Participation at CIRED 2024](#)
- [ERIGrid 2.0's Successful Technical Workshop at AIT](#)
- [ERIGrid 2.0's Many Virtual Facilities](#)
- [Latest Resources](#)

Last Lab Access Call Open Until 30th of September 2024

Up until 30th of September 2024, ERIGrid 2.0 welcomes applications for research stays and remote lab access to our testing facilities within the frame of the 13th and last Lab Access Call. **This will be the last submission possibility in ERIGrid 2.0!**

FREE ACCESS TO SMART GRID AND ENERGY SYSTEMS LABS

Laboratory access can be arranged depending on the conditions at the lab and the applicant's research requirements. Successful applicants will be granted funding covering their travelling expenses, accommodation, all lab operation costs and support of the laboratory staff on site. [Read more...](#)

Register Now for the RI Automation Workshop in Denmark!

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE AUTOMATION WORKSHOP

Start: 24th September 2024 13:00 CEST
End: 25th September 2024 14:00 CEST

Roskilde, Denmark
 Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Risø Campus

Session outline:

- Collaboration: metadata and digital tools for facilitating research collaboration and data exchange
- Automation: how energy system test setups can be repeatable and reproducible (and less complex to handle)
- Coupling of Test Facilities: Methods, Techniques and Technologies to couple large scale test resources from multiple RIs
- Live Laboratory Demonstration

ERIGrid 2.0's Successful Participation at CIRED 2024

The ERIGrid 2.0 Project successfully participated in CIRED (International Community on Electricity Distribution) 2024 held in Vienna, Austria on 19th-20th June.

CIRED is one of Europe's most important conference series for electricity distribution engineers. The ERIGrid 2.0 team was very glad to be able to join the conference and show the project's work.

Thank you all who stopped by our booth to learn more about ERIGrid 2.0!

ERIGrid 2.0's Many Virtual Facilities

ERIGrid 2.0 allows **free access to 10 virtual facilities**. The access to the virtual facilities requires no specific application and user proposals are not submitted to a selection process. One of these facilities is **RSE's DER-TF Daas** which is a platform that provides the access to historical and real-time data of a real Low Voltage microgrid. The infrastructure is composed by a time series database (TSDB) and an object storage (topology, assets, test case description) that is accessible through a web-interface that allows to explore the information at component and system level. **The Virtual Lab**, another facility, is an online educational simulation tool that mimics the operation of the actual laboratory microgrid of EES lab of ICCS. A mathematical model of the laboratory microgrid has been developed along with a friendly GUI. The user can observe several variables (e.g., voltage, active power, reactive power etc.) and perform several actions (e.g., change the power factor of the inverter). The simulation tool includes two different laboratory setups and corresponding experiments: voltage control, and microgrid operation.

Find out about many more in the Virtual Facilities on the [Lab Access page](#).

Latest Resources

- [A Predictive Tool for Techno-Economical Analyses of Renewable Energy Communities](#)
- [Assessing the Provision of a Multi-Ancillary Service Framework provided by PV-BESS Systems \(PhoMSE\) - LAB Experiments](#)
- [Advanced Laboratory Testing Methods Supporting Grid Transition at Pace](#)
- [Challenges and Learnings from Advanced Testing Systems in H2020 ERIGrid 2.0 Project](#)
- [Emerging skill needs and training tools for professionals and researchers in the field of smart energy systems](#)
- [Find all other resources in ERIGrid 2.0 Zenodo community here](#)
- [Find all other resources in ERIGrid 2.0 OpenAIRE here](#)

Keep up with ERIGrid 2.0 news

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Appendix E: Lab Access Slide

The slide features a map of Europe with green highlights in Scandinavia, Germany, and Italy. Two red banners are overlaid on the map: "apply every 3 months for physical lab access" and "access virtual services anytime no application required". To the right, there are four images: a building, a control room, a server room, and a technician working on a device. Below these images is a grid of logos for various research institutions. At the bottom left is the ERIGRID 2.0 Consortium logo and EU H2020 Programme GA No. 870620. At the bottom right is the text "Project Overview and Research Infrastructure Access Possibilities" and the number "8".

ERIGRID 2.0
Connecting European
Smart Grid Infrastructures

apply every 3 months for
physical lab access

access virtual services anytime
no application required

<https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access/>

© The ERIGRID 2.0 Consortium
EU H2020 Programme GA No. 870620

Project Overview and Research Infrastructure Access Possibilities

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Consortium

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